

Annex 1. Draft Questionnaire (Full and Short Versions)

As an optional methodological annex, a structured questionnaire was developed to support potential future empirical validation of the conceptual model. The questionnaire is designed to examine perceptions of digitalisation, digital skills, institutional support, technostress, and labour market participation among older workers. Its structure follows principles of informed consent, data minimisation, and accessibility.

This is a draft questionnaire developed as part of a conceptual research framework and intended for potential future empirical validation.

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Perceptions of Digitalisation, Institutional Support and Participation among Older Workers

Draft Questionnaire (Full Versions)

Section 1. Participant Information

Purpose of the questionnaire:

This questionnaire is part of an analytical initiative developed within COST Action CA21107 “Work Inequalities in Later Life Redefined by Digitalization” (DIGI-net). Its purpose is to explore how older workers perceive digitalisation, institutional support, access to learning opportunities, and labour market participation in the context of ongoing digital transformation.

Estimated completion time:

10–12 minutes

Voluntary participation:

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may stop at any time without giving a reason.

Confidentiality and data protection:

The questionnaire is intended to collect only the minimum information necessary for analytical purposes. Responses should be processed in aggregated form. No directly identifying personal data should be collected unless strictly necessary. If contact data are collected for follow-up purposes, they should be stored separately from the survey responses. Participants should be informed of their rights regarding access, rectification, erasure, restriction, and complaint under EU data protection rules.

Contact information:

Name of researcher

Institution

Email

Section 2. Informed Consent

Consent statement:

Before proceeding, please confirm the following:

1. I have read and understood the information provided above.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary.
3. I understand that I may stop completing the questionnaire at any time.
4. I understand how my responses will be used.
5. I agree to participate in this questionnaire.

Response format:

- Yes, I agree to participate
- No, I do not agree

If “No,” the questionnaire should end automatically.

Section 3. Background Information

1. **What is your age group?**
 - 50–54
 - 55–59
 - 60–64
 - 65 and above
2. **What is your gender?**
 - Female
 - Male
 - Prefer to self-describe: _____
 - Prefer not to say
3. **Which country do you currently live in?**
 - [Drop-down list or short answer]
4. **Do you currently live in:**
 - Urban area
 - Suburban area
 - Rural area
5. **What is your highest level of education completed?**
 - Primary education
 - Secondary education
 - Vocational education
 - Bachelor’s degree
 - Master’s degree
 - Doctoral degree

- Other: _____
- 6. **What is your current employment status?**
 - Full-time employed
 - Part-time employed
 - Self-employed
 - Unemployed
 - Retired but still working
 - Retired and not working
 - Other: _____
- 7. **In which sector do you mainly work / did you most recently work?**
 - Public sector
 - Private sector
 - Non-profit / NGO sector
 - Agriculture
 - Industry / manufacturing
 - Services
 - Education / research
 - Health / care
 - Other: _____

Section 4. Digitalisation and Work

Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements.

Response scale for Items 8–17:

- 1 — Strongly disagree
 - 2 — Disagree
 - 3 — Neither agree nor disagree
 - 4 — Agree
 - 5 — Strongly agree
8. Digital technologies have significantly changed the way work is performed in my field.
 9. My work requires continuous adaptation to new digital tools or systems.
 10. I feel that the pace of digital change in my work environment is very fast.
 11. Digitalisation has increased the complexity of work tasks.
 12. Digitalisation has improved the efficiency of my work.
 13. Digitalisation has created new opportunities for older workers.
 14. Digitalisation has made it more difficult for some older workers to remain employed.
 15. Digitalisation has increased pressure to learn new skills.
 16. Digitalisation has improved flexibility in work arrangements.

17. Digitalisation has changed the balance between experience and technical skills in the workplace.

Section 5. Digital Skills and Learning

Response scale for Items 18–27:

1 — Strongly disagree

2 — Disagree

3 — Neither agree nor disagree

4 — Agree

5 — Strongly agree

18. I feel confident using digital tools required in my work.

19. I have sufficient basic digital skills for everyday work tasks.

20. I have sufficient advanced digital skills for more complex tasks.

21. I have access to training opportunities that help me improve my digital skills.

22. Training opportunities available to me are adapted to my learning needs.

23. I would benefit more from practical and hands-on digital training than from theoretical courses.

24. I feel motivated to continue improving my digital skills.

25. Financial costs make it difficult for me to participate in training.

26. Lack of time makes it difficult for me to participate in training.

27. Older workers should receive more tailored support for digital upskilling.

Section 6. Institutional and Organisational Support

Response scale for Items 28–36:

1 — Strongly disagree

2 — Disagree

3 — Neither agree nor disagree

4 — Agree

5 — Strongly agree

28. My employer / organisation provides sufficient support for adapting to digital changes.

29. My employer values the contribution of older workers during digital transformation.

30. Older workers in my organisation have equal access to training opportunities.

31. Age stereotypes affect how older workers are treated in digitally changing workplaces.

32. Organisational policies in my workplace support lifelong learning.

33. Flexible work arrangements help older workers remain active in the labour market.

34. Government policies in my country sufficiently support older workers in the digital labour market.

35. Public employment or training services are accessible to older workers.

36. More age-inclusive labour market policies are needed in the context of digitalisation.

Section 7. Technostress, Health and Well-being

Response scale for Items 37–45:

1 — Strongly disagree

2 — Disagree

3 — Neither agree nor disagree

4 — Agree

5 — Strongly agree

37. I often feel stressed when I have to use new digital technologies.

38. I find it difficult to keep up with constant technological changes.

39. I sometimes feel overwhelmed by the digital demands of work.

40. Digital technologies sometimes interfere with my work-life balance.

41. Working with digital tools causes physical discomfort (e.g. eye strain, headaches, neck or back pain).

42. My work environment is ergonomically adapted to digital work.

43. Digital technologies can improve health and well-being when used appropriately.

44. Digital work can increase feelings of isolation if support is lacking.

45. Better organisational support could reduce digital stress for older workers.

Section 8. Labour Market Participation and Future Outlook

Response scale for Items 46–53:

1 — Strongly disagree

2 — Disagree

3 — Neither agree nor disagree

4 — Agree

5 — Strongly agree

46. I feel able to remain active in the labour market under current digital conditions.

47. Digitalisation has increased the risk of job loss for older workers.

48. Older workers are at a disadvantage compared to younger workers in the digital labour market.

49. Experience and professional knowledge of older workers remain highly valuable despite digital change.

50. I would be willing to continue working longer if I had appropriate digital and organisational support.

51. Teleworking and digital collaboration tools can help older workers stay employed longer.

52. Current labour market policies should better support older workers' participation.

53. Inclusion of older workers should be a priority in digital transformation strategies.

Section 9. Open-Ended Questions

54. In your opinion, what is the biggest challenge older workers face in the context of digitalisation?

55. What kind of support would most help older workers remain active in the labour market?

56. Do you have any additional comments or observations related to digitalisation and older workers?

Draft Short Questionnaire (Condensed Version)

A shortened version of the questionnaire (24 items) was developed to ensure higher response rates and practical applicability. The structure focuses on key dimensions identified in the analysis, including digitalisation, skills, institutional support, and well-being.

Section 1. Participant Information

Purpose:

This questionnaire explores how digitalisation affects older workers (50+) in terms of skills, participation, and well-being.

Time:

5–7 minutes

Voluntary participation:

Participation is voluntary. You may stop at any time.

Data protection:

Responses are anonymous and used only for analytical purposes.

Section 2. Consent

Do you agree to participate in this questionnaire?

- Yes
- No

if No → end form

Section 3. Background

1. Age group:

- 50–54
- 55–59
- 60–64
- 65+

2. Gender:

- Female
- Male
- Other / Prefer not to say

3. Area of residence:

- Urban
- Rural

4. Employment status:

- Employed
- Self-employed
- Unemployed
- Retired

Section 4. Digitalisation and Work

(Scale: 1 — Strongly disagree → 5 — Strongly agree)

5. Digital technologies have changed my work significantly.
6. My work requires continuous learning of new digital tools.
7. The pace of digital change is difficult to keep up with.
8. Digitalisation creates new opportunities for older workers.

Section 5. Skills and Training

(Scale 1–5)

9. I feel confident using digital tools.
10. I have access to digital training opportunities.
11. Training programs are adapted to my needs.
12. I would benefit more from practical (hands-on) learning.
13. Lack of time or money limits my ability to learn new skills.

Section 6. Support and Inclusion

(Scale 1–5)

14. My organisation supports older workers in adapting to digital change.
15. Older workers have equal access to training opportunities.
16. Age stereotypes affect opportunities in the workplace.
17. Government policies support older workers in the digital economy.

Section 7. Well-being and Technostress

(Scale 1–5)

18. I feel stressed when using new digital technologies.
19. Digital work affects my physical well-being (e.g. eyes, back, fatigue).
20. Digital tools can improve quality of life if used properly.

Section 8. Labour Market Participation

(Scale 1–5)

21. I feel able to remain active in the labour market.
22. Digitalisation increases the risk of job loss for older workers.
23. Flexible work (e.g. remote work) helps older workers stay employed.

Section 9. Open Question

24. What is the biggest challenge older workers face in the digital labour market?